

TEACHING MANAGEMENT OF ISLAMIC CULTURAL HISTORY MULTIMEDIA-BASED TO IMPROVE STUDENT'S AKHLAKUL KARIMAH (STUDY CASE AT MADRASAH ALIYAH MANBA'UL HUDA AND MADRASAH ALIYAH NURROHMAH)

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Abstract

The background to this research is the large number of delinquencies committed by teenagers in Indonesia. This delinquency is not ordinary delinquency but has also crossed over and entered the realm of law. The research objectives, in general, aim to describe and analyze: (a) SKI teaching planning; (b) Organizing SKI learning; (c) Implementation of SKI learning; (d) Evaluation of SKI learning; (e) Barriers in SKI teaching management; f) Multimedia-based SKI teaching management solution. This research uses a qualitative approach and the type of research is descriptive research. The data collection method uses observation interviews and documentation studies. The theoretical basis is George Terry's management theory and Al-Ghazali's theory of akhlakul karimahs. This research uses a qualitative approach and data collection techniques are carried out through observation, interviews and documentation studies. Data sources through triangulation. The policy used in the research is Law no. 20 of 2003 Article 3 and KMA No. 183 of 2019. The results of research in these two madrasas show: planning, organizing, implementing and assessing SKI teaching has been carried out well. Barriers to multimedia-based SKI teaching management are: (a) Lack of student interest in SKI learning; (b) Teachers do not use many teaching methods; (c) The budget is insufficient. The solution to the obstacles is: (a) Always motivating students so that students' interest arises in wanting to continue teaching SKI; (b) Conducting SKI teacher KKG meetings; (c) Apart from receiving funds from the government, madrasas also receive funds from donors, canteens and the sale of sacrificial animals. The research conclusion is that both madrasas have implemented management functions well, although there are still one or more management functions that need to be optimized because this will have an impact on improving students' akhlakul karimah.

Keywords: Management, Islamic Cultural History, Multimedia, Akhlakul Karimah.

INTRODUCTION

Teaching the History of Islamic Culture is a subject in PAI teaching which discusses the story of the human past, both regarding the results of thoughts, the totality of thought and the work of people who lived and lived under the banner of Islam which is based on the understanding of Muslims, the story of the human past. both regarding the results of thoughts, the totality of thought and the work of people who live and live under the banner of Islam which is based on the understanding of Islamic people (Eni Rifriyanti, 2019: 3) The steps for teaching the History of Islamic Culture include planning, organizing, implementing and evaluating. This is in line with George Terry (1958) in Rifaldi (2023: 5) that the management function consists of four basic management functions, namely Planning, Organizing, Actuating and Controlling.

This step will be successful if you use multimedia. Multimedia teaching is teaching that uses several media such as text, video and images. This is in line with Munir (2015) that multimedia teaching is a teaching program that combines text, video and images with computer assistance which aims to achieve teaching outcomes (<https://katulis.com/pengertian-multimedia-pembelajaran-menurut-para-ahli/>). To achieve teaching outcomes, teachers must understand teaching management. teaching management is the activity of managing the teaching process, so teaching management is a very important part of a series of activities in education management. Ardiansyah stated that teaching management in a broad sense contains the process of managing how to teach students with activities starting from planning, organizing, implementing and supervising. Meanwhile, teaching management in the narrow sense is defined as activities that need to be managed by teachers during the interaction process with students in implementing teaching (Ajat Rukajat, 2018:5).

This teaching management should be used by SKI teachers. The History of Islamic Culture (SKI) is a record of development the life journey of Muslim humans from time to time in worship, muamalah and akhlakul karimah as well as in developing a system of life or spreading the teachings of the Islamic religion which is based on faith. This is in line with the Regulation of the Minister of Religion of the Republic of Indonesia in the attachment to Chapter III of the 2013 PAI and Arabic Content Standards. According to Fatikhah (2011: 4) Islamic Cultural History is a science that reveals, investigates and provides related facts and events. with aspects of Muslim life as a whole from the time of the Prophet Muhammad until now.

The management steps for teaching Islamic Cultural History include: planning, organizing, actuating and controlling. Planning is a reference to a person's success in achieving goals. Likewise, an educator should plan. According to George Terry (1986) in Trans. J Smith, planning can mean including the act of selecting and connecting facts and making and using assumptions about the future in terms of visualizing and formulating proposed activities that are considered necessary to achieve the desired results. In this planning, the teacher puts it into the syllabus and teaching Implementation Plan (RPP) to achieve Graduate Competency Standards (SKL). These written documents become operational guidelines for educators in carrying out teaching in the classroom. This syllabus and RPP must be outlined based on Government Regulation Number 13 of 2015 article 1 (18), "Syllabus is a teaching plan for a particular subject or theme which includes Core Competencies, Basic Competencies, teaching materials, teaching activities, assessment, time allocation, and teaching resources".

Crimes committed by Indonesian youth are increasing. This is based on 2016 UNICEF data showing that violence against fellow teenagers in Indonesia is estimated to reach 50 percent. Meanwhile, according to 2017 data from the Indonesian Ministry of Health, there were 3.8 percent of pupils and students who stated that they had abused narcotics and dangerous drugs (<https://fkkmk.ugm.ac.id/kekerasan-juvenile-indonesia-mencapai-50-persen>).

This phenomenon is confirmed by data from 2018 for the first semester, KPAI (Indonesian Child Protection Commission) has handled 1,885 cases of children in conflict with the law (ABH), such as being a drug offender, stealing, and imakhlakul karimahity being the most common cases. From the 2011-2018 data, ABH occupies the top position. In ABH cases, most

of the children were admitted to the Special Children's Correctional Institution (LPKA) because 23.9 percent were stolen, 17.8 percent were in drug cases, 13.2 percent were in imakhlakul karimah cases, and other cases. The causes of children committing crimes are caused by the factors of opportunity, intention, and then the environment (Suriyati, 2022:2). The number of children who become perpetrators of violence has increased by 10 percent (detik.com, 2014).
Research

Conducted in 2014 Stated that of a total 63 million Indonesian teenagers, 14.4 million Indonesian teenagers had ever consumed alcoholic drinks (republika, 2008). In other words, there are 23 percent of Indonesian teenagers who have been involved in alcohol, even though in 2007, teenagers who were involved in alcohol were 4.9 percent. Thus there is an increase in teenagers who are involved in the use of alcohol.

Data shows that of the four million people in Indonesia who abuse drugs, 22 percent of them are young people who are still in school and university and generally the users are 15-20 years old (megapolitan, 2014). Based on the data above, it can be concluded that the behavior or akhlakul karimah of the younger generation in Indonesia is increasingly deteriorating. This must be corrected as soon as possible. With the very rapid development of technology, the entire Indonesian nation is children and adults certainly use sophisticated tools such as smartphones and laptops, or other electronic devices. They often watch various kinds of films, songs, etc. where the pictures are very interesting and colorful. This certainly greatly affects the condition of students in studying at school. If educators only use the lecture method or do not use media that attracts students, it will make students feel bored and less able to absorb the material. It is hoped that SKI teaching using multimedia can maximize teaching of Islamic Cultural History. Students are expected to enjoy teaching SKI or be able to absorb the material provided so they can understand and apply it in everyday life. It is hoped that students can take the blessings of their predecessors, such as: toughness, enthusiasm, generosity, empathy, honesty, fairness, and so on. According to Oemar Hamalik in Lutfan (2019: 24) that: "New discoveries in the fields of science and technology have a huge influence on the field of education. As a result of these influences, education is increasingly progressing, thus encouraging various reform efforts. "In advanced schools, various types of teaching media are used which are in line with the demands of the times. teaching media is part of the teaching resources in which the teaching and teaching process is delivered."

The use of multimedia is expected to improve students' akhlakul karimah. A student's akhlakul karimah are all the good deeds that a student produces without thought and consideration, these characteristics become the main character traits and can increase the student's dignity in the eyes of others. Based on the results of the researcher's research at the beginning of the research, in the city of Bandung, the majority of educational units have carried out the process of teaching the History of Islamic Culture using multimedia. Based on the results of research by researchers in several previous studies, teaching the history of Islamic culture at madrasahh Aliyah Bandung City has a big impact on students' akhlakul karimah. The akhlakul karimah of madrasahh Aliyah students in Bandung City have honest akhlakul karimah, do not give up easily, have high teaching motivation, good manners, high tolerance and have a high leadership

attitude. Based on the background of this problem, the author formulated a dissertation with the title "Teaching Management of Islamic Cultural History to Improve Students' Akhlakul Karimah (Case Study at madrasah Aliyah Manba'ul Huda and Madrasah Aliyah Nurrohmah Bandung City).

METHOD

Based on the background and problem formulation that has been stated in above, the approach taken is Field research (field research) This research uses qualitative research. Qualitative research is research that produces descriptive data in the form of written or spoken words from people or observable behavior. This approach is expected to be capable produce in-depth descriptions of behavior, speech and writing that researchers can observe in students and supervising teachers to be applied at MA Manba'ul Huda. This research aims to describe and analyze social phenomena from the perspective of participants (people who were interviewed, observed and asked data) using words, no using numbers.

Research subject

Research subjects are "subjects intended to be studied by researchers". The subjects in this research were the head of the madrasah and the SKI teacher MA Manba'ul Huda, the head of the madrasah

Method of Collecting Data

The research methods that the author uses to collect the required data are as follows: a) Method observation. In this research, the author came directly to the research location to collect the necessary data; b) Interview method. The author uses a direct interview method, namely when conducting interviews with participants. The author prepares a list of questions that have been compiled and respondents are given the opportunity to answer. The author uses the documentation method. The documentation method is used to obtain data related to documents or archives obtained in research, namely the history of the founding of MA Manba'ul Huda, organizational structure and other data related to multimedia-based SKI teaching management to improve akhlakul karimah. student's character.

Data analysis

If the data has been collected, the next step is to analyze the data, namely processing the data to draw conclusions. In this case the author uses qualitative descriptive analysis techniques, namely describing phenomena that exist at present or in the past, from all data from observations, interviews and documentation. This research describes a condition as it is based on data obtained without any manipulation or change of data, with analysis stages: First, the data that has been obtained is sorted or reduced (categorizing data and removing unnecessary ones); second, presenting the reduced data in narrative form; and the last is drawing conclusions from the data that has been presented.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Research sites

This research took place at madrasah Aliyah Manba'ul Huda on Jalan Cijawura Girang IV, Bandung City. Postal Code: 40286.

History of the Establishment of MA Manba'ul Huda

Islamic Association Islamic Boarding School 110 Manba'ul Huda started with the presence of a figure from Islamic Association (PERSIS) Al-Ustadz H. Itoh Qomaruddin (late) around the 1960s in Cijawura Excited. At that time, he wanted to revive Islamic Ghirah based on the Koran and As-Sunnah in the area around where he lived.

The first activity carried out was a public recital which was held regularly every Friday night for the people of Cijawura Girang and its surroundings at his private house on Jalan Cijawura Girang IV.

As time goes by, every year, the number of students interested in studying at the Manba'ul Huda madrasah increases and requires more adequate attention and facilities. In 1963, a madrasah building measuring 10 x 8 m was built as a place for educational activities, located next to the mosque. In 1983, Al-Ustadz H. Itoh Qomaruddin died. As for the person in charge of the activities of the Manba'ul Huda mosque and madrasah, his position was replaced by Al-Ustadz H. Amin Al-Husaeni who is also his eldest son.

In 1989, the madrasah received a waqf area of 489 m² located to the south of the old Mosque and Madrasha building from Hj. Anikah is the mother of H. Amin Al-Husaeni. In that same year, with available funds, construction began on a permanent madrasah building consisting of 2 floors, construction of which began in 1989 and was completed in 1992. On January 12 1996, at the same time as the inauguration of the name Pesantren Pesantren Pesantren Islam 110 from the Central Leadership Islamic Unity, the Tsanawiyah level of education was also inaugurated, which is still ongoing, and even currently has Mu'allimin and madrasah Ibtidaiyah levels.

Management is a process of several actions in achieving goals, as George R. Terry stated in Hasibuan (2014: 2) that: "Management is a typical process consisting of planning, organizing, moving and controlling actions to determine and achieve goals through utilization human resources and other resources".

Teaching is an interactive process between students and educators. This is in line with Republic of Indonesia Law no. 20 of 2003 concerning Education Systems, teaching is an interactive process of students with educators and teaching resources in a teaching environment. Likewise, Sudjana's opinion in Muhlasin (2019: 69) states that teaching is a planned and basic effort, through a process of "action" (one-way communication between teachers and students).

Alben Ambarita and Suryosubroto, as quoted by Asep Suhendi Arifin (2013) explained that teaching management activities are making teaching plans, implementing teaching, monitoring and evaluating as an evaluation of the teaching that has been carried out.

a. Teaching Planning of Islamic Cultural History (SKI) Multimedia-Based to Improve Students' Akhlakul Karimah at MA Manba'ul Huda

Based on the results of interviews, documentation studies, and observations regarding multimedia-based SKI teaching planning to improve students' akhlakul karimah, SKI teacher MA Manba'ul Huda prepared a plan in the form of:

1) Annual Program

According to Suharsimi Arikunto (1988) a program is a series of activities that will be carried out to achieve a certain goal. The planning aspect is a very important activity in implementing teaching, including planning teaching about the History of Islamic Culture. SKI teacher MA Manba'ul Huda has designed a SKI teaching plan that has teaching goals and objectives using appropriate teaching resources. Teaching planning begins with preparing an annual program. This annual program is a program that will be carried out within a year. The annual program prepared by the SKI madrasah Aliyah Manba'ul Huda teacher consists of Basic Competencies and Time Allocation. This is in accordance with Minister of Education and Culture Regulation Number 24 of 2016 concerning Basic Competencies (KD) in subjects and The Academic Calendar (kaldik) is the basis for developing annual programs.

2) Semester Program

SKI teacher MA Manba'ul Huda has prepared a Semester Program. This Semester Program is a program developed based on the Annual Program. madrasah Aliyah Manba'ul Huda SKI teacher prepares the Semester Program. The semester program prepared by SKI MA teacher Manba'ul Huda is in accordance with those determined by the National Education Standards Agency.

3) Syllabus

Rusman stated that, planning the teaching process includes the syllabus and teaching implementation plan (RPP). (1). Syllabus as a reference for developing teaching implementation plans. In practice, syllabus development can be carried out by teachers independently or by subject teacher deliberation groups (MGMP). (2). RPP is described in the syllabus to direct student teaching activities in an effort to achieve basic competencies (Rusman in Setyowati, 2021: 5)

SKI teacher MA Manba'ul Huda has developed the syllabus well. The syllabus consists of identification, competency standards, basic competencies and main material, teaching activities. This is according to the Ministry of Education and Culture's Education and Training Center (2016: 13).

SKI teacher MA Manba'ul Huda in preparing the syllabus took several steps, namely: reviewing Competency Standards and Basic Competencies. Competency Standards and Basic Competencies can be taken from content standards which are usually standard, except that those which do not yet exist can be prepared by the syllabus compiler/developer themselves. The next step is identifying the main/teaching material, identifying the main/teaching material that supports the achievement of basic competencies. Then the SKI teacher develops teaching

activities. teaching activities are designed to provide teaching experiences that involve mental and physical processes through interactions between students, students and educators, the environment and other teaching resources in order to achieve basic competencies.

SKI teachers formulate achievement indicators. Competency Indicators are markers of the achievement of basic competencies which are characterized by measurable changes in behavior which include attitudes, knowledge and skills. Indicators are developed according to the characteristics of students, subjects, educational units, regional potential and are formulated in operational verbs that are measurable and/or observable. Indicators are used as a basis for compiling evaluation tools.

The SKI teacher determines the type of evaluation. Evaluation of students' achievement of basic competencies is carried out based on indicators. Evaluation is carried out using tests and non-tests in written and oral form, performance observations, attitude measurements, evaluation of work results in the form of assignments, projects and/or products, use of portfolios, and self-evaluation. The evaluation system must be adjusted to the teaching experiences undertaken in the teaching process.

The next step is for the SKI teacher to determine the allocation. Time: Determining the time allocation for each basic competency is based on the effective number of weeks and the time allocation for subjects per week. SKI teachers determine teaching resources. The steps for developing the syllabus are based on the Ministry of Education and Culture's Employee Education and Training Center Team (2016; 14-16). In this way, the SKI teacher MA Manba'ul Huda has prepared the syllabus well. The definition of syllabus is explained in Government Regulation (PP) no. 13 of 2015.

4) Teaching Implementation Plan

Based on Minister of Education and Culture Regulation Number 103 of 2014 concerning teaching in Basic Education and Secondary Education, the components and systematics of the teaching Implementation Plan (RPP) are determined. In preparing the RPP, SKI teacher Manba'ul Huda took several steps based on the Ministry of Education and Culture's Pusdiklat Team (2016: 22):

1. Review SKL, SK/KI-KD, indicators and syllabus to explore competency achievements and identify opportunities for teaching activities

2. Determine identity.

- Write down the Competency Standards/core competencies/stages for achieving development in the syllabus.
- Rewrite the basic competencies in the syllabus.
- Write down the indicators that have been formulated in the syllabus.
- Formulate teaching objectives.

Based on the steps above, the MA Manba'ul Hud teacher has prepared a lesson plan well. The lesson plans that have been prepared by SKI teachers at MA Manba'ul Huda are in accordance with the 2013 curriculum. The format of the lesson plans that have been prepared based on data obtained by researchers is in accordance with Minister of Education and Culture Regulation No. 81A of 2013 concerning the preparation of the 2013 curriculum RPP which states that: A teaching Implementation Plan is a teaching plan that is developed in detail from a particular main material or theme that refers to the syllabus. The RPP for the History of Islamic Culture is in accordance with Minister of National Education Regulation no. 65 of 2013 concerning Primary and Secondary Education Process Standards in the 2013 curriculum, states that teaching objectives are applied with competency standards, core competencies and indicators, which are described in detail about the competencies expected after the teaching process is completed.

3. Teaching Organizing of Islamic Cultural History (SKI) Multimedia-Based to Improve students' Akhlakul Karimah

Organizing is a process of determining, grouping and arranging various activities needed to achieve goals, placing people in each activity, providing the necessary tools, determining authority that is relatively delegated to each individual who will carry out the activities. (Hasibuan, 2007: 19).

Organizing teaching becomes a benchmark for teaching activities so that the direction and responsibility are clear. This allows the principal's position as a manager in preparing teaching facilities and infrastructure, clearing the duties and functions of educators to select and design teaching activities in accordance with time distribution, curriculum engineering, media and teaching components.

SKI teachers organize several teaching components, including:

1) Curriculum

Curriculum means a number of knowledge or subjects that students must take and complete in order to achieve a level or diploma. The curriculum used by MA Manba'ul Huda for class XI is the 2013 curriculum. The 2013 curriculum contains activities: observing, asking questions, gathering information, associating, communicating. This is in accordance with Minister of Education and Culture Regulation no. 103 of 2014. observing, asking, gathering information, associating, and communicating are the stages of teaching in the 2013 curriculum with a scientific approach which is student-centered teaching.

The 2013 curriculum encourages and prioritizes student activity to develop understanding of knowledge, skills and spiritual and social attitudes in students. So students have to do a lot of activities, move a lot, interact a lot, discuss a lot, do a lot of group work, explore a lot of knowledge, observe a lot, ask a lot, gather information a lot, associate a lot, communicate a lot. All this will increase the dynamics in the class.

2) Teaching Materials

SKI teacher MA Manba'ul prepares teaching materials in accordance with teaching materials based on the syllabus. teaching material is the content of a curriculum, namely in the form of subjects or fields of study with topics, sub-topics and detailed explanations. The purpose of implementing teaching is visible in the teaching material delivered to students. Syaiful Bahri Djamarah explained that teaching material is the essence of what will be conveyed in the implementation of teaching. Without teaching materials, the implementation of teaching will not run well (Djamarah in Umami, 2020: 9). Teachers pay attention to the criteria in selecting teaching materials, including that the materials must be appropriate to the teaching objectives, explained, in accordance with students' needs, arranged systematically, and should come from standard books.

SKI teachers in determining the teaching materials given to students need to be chosen appropriately, so that they can help students achieve competency standards and the teaching objectives they wish to achieve. Based on the research results, SKI teachers provide teaching materials such as books. Teachers refer to teacher books, student books, and books that are relevant to the teaching material, as well as from the internet. According to the Directorate of Senior High School Development (2008:6), teaching materials are all forms of materials used to assist teachers in carrying out teaching and teaching activities. The material in question can be written or unwritten material. Meanwhile, according to Koesnandar (2008:6), the types of teaching materials based on subject consist of two types, including: (a) teaching materials that are deliberately designed for teaching, such as books, handouts, worksheets and modules; (b) teaching materials that are not designed but can be used for teaching, for example clippings, newspapers, films, advertisements or news.

3) Teaching Media

Looking at the RPP prepared by the SKI teacher at MA Manba'ul Huda regarding the use of teaching media, the SKI teacher uses teaching media such as picture media, power point media and textbooks, and uses teaching Aids (ABP). teaching Aids (ABP) include whiteboards, markers and LCDs when using power point media or watching videos.

SKI teachers have used teaching media in accordance with the teaching material presented. This is in accordance with Sadiman's opinion in Rani et al (2019: 9) who state that media is anything that can be used to channel messages from the sender to the recipient so that it can stimulate students' thoughts, feelings, attention and interests in such a way that the teaching process occurs...

SKI teachers use various teaching media. This aims to attract students' attention, to make it easier for students to absorb the knowledge provided by the teacher, so that students have cognitive, affectional and compensatory abilities. Levie & Lentz (1982) proposed four functions of teaching media in the Teaching and teaching process, especially visual media: (1) attention function, (2) affective function, (3) cognitive function, (5) compensatory function.

SKI teacher MA Manba'ul Huda uses multimedia because of its many advantages, namely: students can learn according to their abilities and desires, students learn from teachers who are patient like computers and follow technological developments. This is in accordance with Fenrich in Munir (2013) concluding that the advantages of multimedia teaching include: a) Students can learn according to their abilities, readiness and desires; b) Students learn from 'patient' tutors (such as computers) who adapt to the students' abilities; c) Students will be encouraged to pursue knowledge and obtain instant feedback; d) Students are familiar with information and communication technology devices.

4) Teaching Model

Madrasah Aliyah Manba'ul Huda SKI teacher uses the Discovery teaching model. The disclosure/discovery teaching model (Discovery/Inquiry teaching) is understanding concepts, meanings and relationships through an intuitive process to finally arrive at a conclusion. Discovery occurs when individuals engage primarily in the use of their mental processes to discover some concepts and principles. Discovery is done through observation, classification, measurement, prediction, determination, and inference. The process above is called the cognitive process, while discovery itself is the mental process of assimilating concepts and principles in the mind.

5) Teaching Resources

Teaching sources are essentially anything, whether objects, data, facts, ideas, people, etc. that can lead to a teaching process. For example, textbooks, modules,

LKS (student worksheet), realia, models, markets, banks, museums, zoos and markets (Prastowo in Samsinar, 2019: 2)

Sudjana in Samsinar (2019: 4) divides teaching resources into several categories, namely:

- a) Printed teaching sources: books, magazines, encyclopedias, brochures, newspapers, posters, floor plans, etc.
- b) Non-print teaching sources: films, slides, videos, models, audio cassettes, etc.
- c) Teaching resources in the form of facilities: auditorium, library, study room, studio, sports field, etc.
- d) Teaching resources in the form of activities: interviews, group work, observation, simulations, games, etc.
- e) Teaching resources in the form of the environment: parks, museums, etc.

Because of the importance of material in teaching, teachers must be clever in arranging material. To get a good composition of material, it is very necessary to take it from good teaching sources. This teaching resource is very important. The choice of teaching resources is not arbitrary. In selecting teaching resources teachers use certain criteria to select the teaching resources to be used. This is intended so that the teaching resources selected are appropriate and in accordance with the teaching objectives and are efficient when applied in teaching.

3. Teaching Implementation of Islamic Cultural History (SKI) Multimedia-Based SKI Teaching to Improve Students' Akhlakul Karimah

Teaching implementation is the application of the teaching plans that have been made. The implementation of SKI teaching has been carried out in accordance with the teaching Implementation Plan which has been prepared by the SKI teacher MA Manba'ul Huda. According to Sudjana in Jamil (2018: 119), the implementation of teaching is a process that is arranged in such a way according to certain steps so that the implementation achieves the expected results. Actuating is the implementation of planning on an organizing basis. SKI teaching activities can run well, namely initial activities, core activities and closing activities.

Implementation of SKI teaching about the Abbasid Daula using multimedia. This is because: a) Multimedia is media that combines two or more elements consisting of text, graphics, images, audio, video and animation in an integrated manner; b) Multimedia facilitates student-centered teaching because students are given the freedom to choose their own teaching materials and learn at a level that suits themselves; c) The use of multimedia can raise students' teaching motivation, because the presence of multimedia makes teaching presentations more interesting.

Apart from that, based on the cone of experience revealed by Edgar Dale (in Latuheru, 1988: 10) that the acquisition of teaching outcomes through the sense of sight and hearing is 75%, through the sense of hearing 13% and through other senses around 12%.

From the research above, it can be concluded how the teaching material can be achieved if in teaching and teaching activities teachers only rely on lectures, according to Edgar Dale, only 13%. Other research results show that teaching and teaching activities will be more effective and easier if assisted by visual means, where 11% of what is learned occurs through the sense of hearing, while 83% occurs through the sense of sight. Besides that, it is stated that we can only remember 20% of what we hear, but can remember 50% of what we see and hear. By using multimedia, SKI teaching can improve students' akhlakul karimah. By using multimedia, material that is abstract and outside students' daily experience can be understood, students do not feel bored and difficult material becomes easier.

With the existence of educational technology, it will be easier to produce educational media. From experience, teachers begin to learn that students have different ways of teaching, some learn faster through audio-visuals, some learn faster through audio, some prefer using print media, others through multimedia and so on (Sadiman, 2002: 9).

Evaluation of Multimedia-Based SKI teaching to Improve 4. Student Akhlakul Karimah To determine the achievement of SKI teaching, the SKI teacher MA Manba'ul Huda has the task of carrying out an evaluation. Evaluation is the collection of information. This is in accordance with Teguh Triwiyanto that evaluation is a systemic process, including collecting information (numbers, descriptions and verbal), analysis, interpretation of information to make decisions. Assessment is carried out by: (1) educators (internal), planned and carried out by education during the teaching process (quality assurance); (2) education unit (internal); (3) assessing SKL achievement or as a basis for consideration of graduation, carried out by the government

(external) as a quality controller. The evaluation carried out by the Cultural History teacher MA Manba'ul Huda consists of assignments, formative, mid-semester evaluation and final semester evaluation. These evaluations measure students' cognitive, affective and psychomotor skills. Evaluation is carried out to measure the extent of students' abilities after experiencing the teaching and teaching process. Other evaluations include work evaluations in the form of assignments, portfolios and self-evaluations. The portfolio evaluation carried out by SKI MA teacher Manba'ul Huda was making canvases, posters, quotes. The average knowledge and skills score for XI MIA is above the KKM. Class XI IIS results for knowledge and skills scores above KKM. The spiritual attitude of MA Manba'ul Huda students, where the content of the student's spiritual attitude assessment is: I am happy that Islam has an extraordinary history, which is good. The indicator that I believe in the truth of Islam is good. I pray that being able to pursue higher education will be very good, I pray that Islamic scientists will be reborn well, I pray that scientists will be rewarded with the best reward.

As for the social attitudes of students with the indicator that I am interested in studying the history of science in the Islamic world, I get good results, I kiss the teacher's hand when I meet them, I get a good average score, I kiss my parents when I leave school with a very good average, I look after the books and keep them. neatly is very good and I want to tell friends about the history of science in the world is good. Islamic Cultural History (SKI) teacher MA Manba'ul carried out a formative evaluation, namely by observation. This observation is observing student discussions, the result of which is that most students actively participate in discussions. Thus the results are very good.

5. Barriers of Teaching Management of Islamic Cultural History (SKI) Multimedia-based to Improve Student Akhlakul Karimah at MA Manba'ul Huda

SKI teachers have obstacles in managing multimedia-based SKI teaching. Obstacles, MA Manba'ul Huda looked for solutions including:

- a) Lack of student interest in teaching SKI.
- b) SKI teachers do not use a variety of teaching methods.
- c) The budget for teaching is very large.

6. Multimedia-Based SKI teaching Management Solution to Improve Student Akhlakul Karimah at MA Manba'ul Huda

To overcome these obstacles, MA Manba'ul Huda is looking for solutions including:

- a) SKI teachers often motivate students so that students' interest arises in the desire to continue teaching SKI.
- b) SKI teachers use various teaching methods so that students increase their interest in teaching or understand the material being taught more quickly.
- c) The budget for teaching is very large. To overcome this, MA Manba'ul Huda received a budget from student tuition fees, donors and the canteen.

b. Teaching Planning of Islamic Cultural History (SKI) Multimedia-Based to Improve Students' Akhlakul Karimah at MA Nurrohmah

Based on the results of interviews, documentation studies, and observations regarding multimedia-based SKI teaching planning to improve students' akhlakul karimahs, SKI teacher MA Nurrohmah prepared a plan in the form of:

1) Annual Program (Prota)

Approaching the new academic year, the Head of Madrasah Aliyah Nurrohmah provided an academic calendar to be used in creating an annual teaching program for the History of Islamic Culture. Prota or annual program is a plan for determining the allocation of time in one year to achieve the competency standards and basic competencies that have been determined. Prota is developed by teachers for each class. The Annual Program is prepared by SKI teacher MA Nurrohmah before the school year, because its existence will be used as a guide for the development of subsequent programs, such as the Semester Program (promes), Syllabus, and teaching Implementation Plan (RPP). This Annual Program (Prota) contains: Core Competencies (KI), Basic Competencies (KD), and Time Allocation. SKI teacher MA Nurrohmah prepares Prota based on predetermined stages. The Annual Program is structured based on the following stages:

- a) Identify the number of basic competencies and indicators in one year of learning.
- b) Identifying the breadth and depth of basic competencies and indicators.
- c) Analyze the educational calendar and adjust needs based on the characteristics/character of the educational units.
- d) Carry out basic competency mapping for each semester.
- e) Provide markings for holidays, the start of the new school year, effective weeks for studying, and effective hours for studying each week. Pay attention to the effective week for arranging time allocations for each basic competency.
- f) Determine the time allocation required for each subject, basic competencies and subject matter in the effective week. The time allocation provided must be in accordance with the scope of the material, the importance of the material, and the time to review the material.

SKI teachers pay attention to several things when analyzing time allocation, namely:

- a) Determining the number of weeks in a month in a semester/school year looks at the general calendar.
- b) Determining the number of effective and ineffective weeks in each month in the semester/school year by looking at the educational calendar.
- c) Distribution of the number of lesson hours for each lesson unit that has been previously mapped.

- d) Allocation of class hours for daily tests, mid-semester tests and final semester tests.
- e) Distribution of the effective amount of time/hours of lessons in 1 year/semester to all units proportionally and all types of tests.

2) Semester Program (Promes)

SKI teachers prepare the Semester Program based on the Annual Program. This program is a reference for compiling the teaching syllabus. SKI teachers take several steps in preparing the Semester Program, namely:

- a) Determine the Competency Standards (SK) and Basic Competencies (KD) to be achieved. SK and KD are listed in the Content Standards (SI).
- b) Determine the time allocation or number of lesson hours for each Competency Standard and Basic Competency through the annual program that has been prepared
- c) Determine the week or month
- d) Make notes or explanations on certain parts that require further explanation.

This semester program contains:

- a. Identity, starting from educational unit, school name, class, semester, subject, academic year
- b. Fill in, starting from Competency Standards (SK), Basic Competencies (KD), number of teaching meeting hours (JJP) and month

3) Syllabus

SKI teachers prepare the syllabus based on the Semester Program. This syllabus contains: school identity, subjects, classes/programs and semesters, core competencies, basic competencies, main material, teaching activities, evaluation, time allocation and teaching resources. Syllabus development steps carried out by SKI teachers:

1. Review Competency Standards and Basic Competencies.
2. Identifying Material. Main/Learning. Identify the main/learning materials that support the achievement of basic competencies by considering: student potential, level of physical, intellectual, emotional, social and spiritual development of students, benefits for students, scientific structure, student needs and environmental demands
3. Developingteaching Activities.
4. Formulate achievement indicators.
5. Determine the type of evaluation. SKI teachers evaluate students' achievement of basic competencies based on indicators
6. Determine the time allocation. SKI teachers determine the time allocation for each basic competency based on the number of effective weeks and the time allocation for subjects per week.
7. Determineteaching Resources.

4) Teaching Implementation Plan (RPP)

SKI teacher MA Nurrohmah prepares a teaching Implementation Plan (RPP) based on the syllabus. This RPP contains: school name, subjects, class, time allocation, basic competencies, materials. Teaching objectives, teaching activities, media, tools/materials and teaching and evaluation resources. teaching activities consist of preliminary activities, core activities and closing activities.

The teaching material that will be given to students is: evaluating the process of the birth of the Abbasid Daula. teaching objectives: identify the birth process of the Abbasid Daula, identify the achievements of the Abbasid Daula's caliphs, identify the phases of government and leadership of the Abbasid Daulah, identify the expansion of the Abbasid Daula's territory. Media: video, presentation slides (ppt) and materials. Tools/materials: laptop, cellphone, tablet and others. Teaching resources: Teacher and student books, modules, teaching materials, internet, and other relevant sources.

Learning activities consist of: introduction. The activities are: the teacher greets and invites students to pray together (Religious), the teacher checks student attendance, the teacher conveys the objectives and benefits of teaching about the topic to be taught, the teacher conveys an outline of the material coverage and teaching steps.

In the core activities, the SKI teacher provides motivation and guidance for students to look, observe, read and write again. SKI teacher displays and reading materials related to the process of the birth of the Abbasid Daula. The teacher provides the opportunity to identify as many things as possible that are not yet understood, this question must be related to the material on the process of the birth of the Abbasid Daula. Students are given the opportunity to discuss, collect information, present again, and exchange information regarding the process of the birth of the Abbasid Daula (Collecting information and problem solving). Students present the results of their work and then respond to other students (Communication). The teacher and students make conclusions about the things they have learned regarding the process of the birth of the Abbasid Daula. Students are then given the opportunity to ask again about things they have not understood (Creativity).

In the closing activity, the SKI teacher and students reflect on the teaching experience and the teacher presents the teaching plan at the next meeting and prays. In evaluation activities (assessments), teachers carry out attitude observations, knowledge tests (in the form of written tests) and presentations of work or projects with evaluation rubrics as skill scores.

b. Teaching Organizing of Islamic Cultural History (SKI) Multimedia-Based to Improve Students' Akhlakul Karimah

Based on interviews, documentation studies and observations, SKI teachers organize several teaching components that can support success in teaching. The teaching components are:

1) Curriculum

The curriculum used for class XI IIS is the 2013 curriculum. The teaching steps based on the 2013 curriculum are as follows:

The opening teaching activities are greetings, apperception, introduction to material, initial motivation. Core activities include: observing, Questioning, Associating, Experimenting, Creating Networking, Communicating, Implementing. In the closing activity, the SKI teacher concludes, final motivation, enrichment, greetings. This curriculum is expected to produce Indonesian people who are: productive, creative, innovative, affective through strengthening integrated attitudes, skills and knowledge.

2) Teaching Materials

SKI teachers choose material that is appropriate to the subject matter. The aim of organizing this material is to determine the main points of the material to be taught by making a summary. Each subject matter by the SKI teacher is adjusted to the teaching objectives. In making goals or formulating teaching objectives, SKI teachers formulate teaching based on cognitive, affective and psychomotor aspects.

The SKI material at MA Nurrohmah is: various events in the process of the birth of the Abbasid Daula, Achievement Caliphs from the Abbasid Daulah, Development Phases of Government and leadership of the Abbasid Daulah, Expansion of the territory of the Abbasid Daulah, Factors of Civilization Progress of the Abbasid Daulah, Indicators of Civilization Progress of the Abbasid Daulah, Development Civilization in the socio-cultural, political and military fields, the system of government of the Abbasid Daula, the decline of the Abbasid Daula.

3) Teaching Method

SKI teachers plan to use several teaching methods, namely: lecture, discussion, question and answer methods. Usually at the beginning of learning, SKI teachers often use the lecture method. Then the SKI Teacher uses the discussion method. This discussion was carried out by three to four students. The SKI teacher gives assignments related to the Abbasid Daula to students. Then students work in pairs to do the assignment using cellphones. Then the students present the assignment.

To form good akhlakul karimahs, SKI teachers also use exemplary methods, such as: telling about the akhlakul karimahs of the Prophets, the Prophet's friends or figures of the Abbasid Daula. SKI teachers must also have good akhlakul karimahs because they must be role models for their students. Sometimes SKI teachers also use the value clarification method, namely active dialogue in the form of discussions so that students do not experience deviations from life values. By using the various methods above, it is hoped that the formation of akhlakul karimah can be achieved.

4) Teaching Model

The teaching model used by Islamic Cultural History teachers is the Problem Based teaching model. This teaching model is a teaching model that prioritizes students' activeness in critical thinking and is always skilled when faced with solving a problem.

5) Teaching Resources

Teaching resources are very important to help optimize teaching outcomes. Therefore, MA Nurrohmah pays great attention to and equips madrasas with various kinds of teaching resources. The teaching resources used by SKI MA Nurrohmah teachers are the internet and Student Worksheets (LKS), videos, pictures, cellphones, libraries. Students are allowed to bring cellphones and keep them. If the cellphone is needed, students are allowed to use it in the Teaching and teaching Process (PBM). The images used in PBM are usually taken from the internet which are then shown to students using an LCD. When the SKI teacher gives assignments that require information about SKI, the SKI teacher asks students to look for this information in the library.

c. Implementation of Multimedia-Based SKI Teaching to Improve students' Akhlakul Karimah

Based on interviews, documentation studies and observations, SKI teachers carry out several activities, namely:

1. First meeting:

1) Preliminary Activities

The SKI teacher comes to class on time. Before teaching started, the SKI teacher prepared a video about the Abbasid Daula, laptop, LCD and speakers. Students help to install the equipment. A few minutes later, the laptop was connected to the LCD and speakers. After that there are several activities, namely: students say greetings and the teacher invites students to pray together (religiously), the SKI teacher checks the students' attendance. The SKI teacher provides motivation. The SKI teacher conveyed the aims and benefits of teaching about the Abbasid Dynasty. The SKI teacher conveys the material that will be taught, namely: the background of the founding of the Abbasid Dynasty, the history of the founding of the Abbasid Dynasty

2) Core activities

In the core activities, students are given guidance to see, observe, read and write again. The SKI teacher gave a presentation about the Abbasid Dynasty. Students were given a show about the Abbasid Dynasty. Students watch the broadcast carefully. Then the teacher provides reading material about the background to the founding of the Abbasid Dynasty. The teacher provides the opportunity to identify as many things as possible that are not yet understood about the background to the founding of the Abbasid Dynasty: the Abbasids, Humaimah and the thinkers of the Abbasids, the choice of place, the spread of thought, preparations for the Bani Abbas revolution, the history of the founding of the Abbasid Dynasty which consisted of key figures in the founding of the Abbasid Dynasty : Muhammad bin Ali, Ibrahim bin Muhammad, Abu Muslim al-Khurasani, power and trust, commitment to carrying out trust.

Students are given the opportunity to discuss, collect information, present and exchange information regarding the process of the birth of the Abbasid Dynasty. Students present their work and then respond to other students.

Teachers and students are then given the opportunity to ask questions about things they do not understand. Teachers emphasize the akhlakul karimahs of cooperation.

3) Closing Activities

In this closing activity, the SKI teacher and students reflect on the teaching experience. Then the SKI teacher presents the lesson plan at the next meeting and prays.

b. Second meeting.

This meeting consists of several activities:

1) Preliminary Activities:

In this preliminary activity there are several activities, namely: students say greetings and the teacher invites students to pray together (religiously), the SKI teacher checks students' attendance.

The SKI teacher conveys the goals and benefits of teaching about the topic to be taught. The teacher provides an outline of the material coverage and teaching steps. The material coverage is about the Abbasid Dynasty: The development of civilization and science during the Abbasid Dynasty.

2) Core Activities:

Students are given reading material related to the development of civilization and science during the Abbasid Dynasty. Students see, observe, read and write again. The reading material consists of: Assimilation of Arabs and Non-Arabs, the Translation Movement, Progress of Civilization and its Figures: Progress in the Science of Tafsir and Hadith, Progress in Religious Sciences, progress in the Field of Science and Civilization Centers of the Abbasid Dynasty and Buildings Places of Education and Places of Worship. Then the teacher provides the opportunity to identify as many things as possible that are not yet understood.

Students are given the opportunity to discuss, collect information with the help of cellphones, present and exchange information regarding the development of civilization and science during the Abbasid Dynasty. Students present their work and then respond to other students.

The teacher emphasizes the akhlakul karimahs that students must have, like the characters in the videos they watch. The akhlakul karimahs that students must have are: honesty, discipline. Teachers and students make conclusions about things they have learned regarding the development of civilization and science during the Abbasid Dynasty. Students are then given the opportunity to ask questions about things they have not understood.

3) Closing Activities:

In this closing activity, the SKI teacher and students reflect on the teaching experience. After that the SKI teacher presented the lesson plan at the next meeting and prayed.

c. Third meeting

SKI teachers carry outreaching activities, namely:

1) Preliminary Activities

In this preliminary activity there are several activities, namely: students say greetings and the teacher invites students to pray together (religiously), the SKI teacher checks students' attendance. The SKI teacher provides motivation. The SKI teacher conveyed the aims and benefits of teaching about the Ottoman State.

2) Core Activities

Students are given motivation and guidance to see, observe, read and write again. Students were given impressions and reading material related to the process of the birth of the Ottoman Empire. The teacher provides opportunities to identify as many things as possible that are not yet understood.

Students are given the opportunity to discuss, collect information, present again, and exchange information regarding the process of the birth of the Ottoman State. Questions and answers on the akhlakul karimahs of the characters in the Daulah Usmani video, such as: responsibility, compassion, caring for the environment. Students present their work and then respond to other students.

Teachers and students make conclusions about matters related to the process of the birth of the Ottoman State, students are then given the opportunity to ask questions about things they do not understand.

3) Closing Activities

In this closing activity, the SKI teacher and students reflect on the teaching experience. After that the SKI teacher presented the lesson plan at the next meeting and prayed.

4. Teaching Evaluation of Islamic Cultural History (SKI) of Multimedia-Based to Improve Students' Akhlakul Karimah

Based on observations, SKI teachers carry out several evaluations. Among them are:

a. Pre-test

The pre-test was carried out by SKI teachers MA Manba'ul Huda and MA Nurrohmah to find out how much material the students knew before the material was given to the students. Questions were given directly to students orally, namely: how and what was the secret of the Abbasid Dynasty movement so that the Abbasids could survive for five centuries?

b. Post test

The post-test was given by SKI teachers MA Manba'ul Huda and MA Nurrohmah, namely: summarizing Daulah Abbasiyah material resulting from group discussions, presenting the results of the discussion, then uploading it to the SKI teacher's Instagram. In skills evaluation, SKI teachers carry out performance evaluations and project evaluations to assess the skills

possessed by students. Likewise with the Usmani material, the SKI teacher also carried out a formative evaluation, in the form of a portfolio. Portfolio example: are the Turks whose lives like to wander, even though some of their descendants succeeded in establishing a strong Islamic kingdom? Give an argument for your opinion! Describe the golden times when the Ottoman Empire was ruled by Sulaiman al-Qanuni! Give reasons for your answer!

c. Formative

Formative is carried out by SKI teachers after the Abbasid Dynasty material is finished. SKI teachers carry out formative. The questions consist of multiple choice and essay. The evaluation carried out by SKI teachers is not only knowledge but attitudes and skills. Formative evaluation of attitudes, teachers observe students' attitudes when discussing and socializing. The SKI teacher observed students' cooperation, when talking with their friends, enthusiasm for discussion, when presenting the results of the discussion. Skill evaluation, namely students create a concept map about the Abbasid Dynasty.

d. Mid-semester evaluation

The mid-semester evaluation is carried out by the SKI teacher after three months of SKI learning.

e. Final Semester Evaluation

This evaluation was carried out after the SKI teacher provided material on the Abbasid Dynasty, Ottoman Dynasty, Mughal Dynasty and Syafavid Dynasty. The questions are multiple choice and essay. Then the instrument is used to assess attitudinal competence. Giving questions to assess student knowledge is carried out at several stages, when sub-themes and themes are completed, mid-semester and end-of-semester evaluation.

5. Obstacles in Multimedia-Based Management of teaching the History of Islamic Culture to Improve Students' Akhlakul Karimah

Based on interviews, the obstacles in multimedia-based SKI teaching to improve students' akhlakul karimahs are:

- a) Lack of student interest in SKI learning.
- b) The less varied teaching methods used by SKI teachers
- c) The madrasa operational budget is very large. This budget is very important because due to a lack of budget, teachers have difficulty providing teaching aids or SKI teaching media.

5. Teaching Planning of Islamic Cultural History (SKI) at MA Manba'ul Huda and MA Nurrohmah

Management is a process of several actions in achieving goals, as George R. Terry stated in Hasibuan (2014: 2) that: "Management is a typical process consisting of planning, organizing, moving and controlling actions to determine and achieve goals through utilization human resources and other resources".

Learning is an interactive process between students and educators. This is in line with Republic of Indonesia Law no. 20 of 2003 concerning Education Systems, teaching is an interactive process of students with educators and teaching resources in a teaching environment. Likewise, Sudjana's opinion in Muhlasin (2019: 69) states that teaching is a planned and basic effort, through a process of "action" (one-way communication between teachers and students).

Learning planning is a decision-making process resulting from thinking rationally about certain teaching goals and objectives, namely changes in behavior and a series of activities as an effort to achieve a goal by utilizing all existing potential and resources (Zahroh, in Moh. Sopi'i, 2019: 4).

Alben Ambarita and Suryosubroto, as quoted by Asep Suhendi Arifin (2013) explained that teaching management activities are making teaching plans, implementing learning, monitoring and evaluating as an evaluation of the teaching that has been carried out.

MA Manba'ul Huda and MA Nurrohmah have implemented teaching management well. This is because MA Manba'ul Huda and MA Nurrohmah have carried out planning, organizing, implementing and evaluating teaching well.

The SKI teacher has carried out lesson planning. This is because the planning function plays a greater role than other functions, which is in accordance with the opinion of Indartono in Nahidh (2021: 5) which states that planning is the most important process of all management functions because without planning, other functions cannot walk. SKI teachers plan teaching programs. The teaching program includes:

1) Annual Program

According to Suharsimi Arikunto (1988) a program is a series of activities that will be carried out to achieve a certain goal. The planning aspect is a very important activity in implementing learning, including planning teaching about the History of Islamic Culture. SKI teachers MA Manba'ul Huda and MA Nurrohmah have designed a SKI teaching plan that has teaching goals and objectives using appropriate teaching resources.

This is in accordance with Animatul (2014: 126), teaching planning is a decision-making process resulting from thinking rationally about certain teaching goals and objectives, namely changes in behavior and a series of activities that must be carried out as an effort to achieve these goals by utilizing all existing teaching potential and resources.

Learning planning begins with preparing an annual program. This annual program is a program that will be carried out within a year. The annual program prepared by SKI teachers at Madrasah Aliyah Manba'ul Huda and Madrasah Aliyah Nurrohmah consists of Basic Competencies and Time Allocation. This is in accordance with Minister of Education and Culture Regulation Number 24 of 2016 concerning Basic Competencies (KD) for subjects and the Academic Calendar (kaldik) which is the basis for developing annual programs.

SKI teachers at Madrasah Aliyah Manba'ul Huda and Madrasah Nurrohmah took several steps in creating the Annual Program, namely:

- a) Review the educational calendar and the characteristics of schools/madrasahs based on educational unit level needs.
- b) Mark holidays, start of the school year, effective week, study, effective teaching time (per week). Holidays include:
 - 1) Mid-semester break
 - 2) Pause between semesters
 - 3) End of school year holidays
 - 4) Religious holidays
 - 5) Public holidays include national holidays
 - 6) Special holidays
- c. Calculate the number of effective weeks in each month and semester in one year and enter it in the available matrix format
- d. Distribute the allocation of time provided for a subject, for each KD and its discussion topic in the effective week, according to the scope of the material, the level of difficulty and importance of the material, as well as considering the time for tests and review of the material. Determination of Time Allocation is based on the number of lesson hours in accordance with the applicable curriculum structure and the breadth of material that must be mastered by students. This is in line with Ahmad Sodikiy & Djunaidatul Munawwarah (2011: 22).

Semester Program

SKI teachers MA Manba'ul Huda and MA Nurrohmah have prepared the Semester Program. This Semester Program is a program developed based on the Annual Program. Madrasah SKI teachers Aliyah Manba'ul Huda and MA Nurrohmah prepared the Semester Program. The semester program prepared by SKI teachers MA Manba'ul Huda and MA Nurrohmah is in accordance with those determined by the National Education Standards Agency.

This Semester Program functions to:

- Make the teacher's task easier when holding lessons for one semester
- Able to direct activities to achieve the programmed teaching objectives
- Becomes a basic pattern for organizing the duties and authority of each party participating in the learning
- Become a teacher's guide in work and study
- Becomes a benchmark of effectiveness in the teaching process

Becomes a material for compiling data, so that work balance is formed

Able to save time, energy, costs and supporting tools because teaching can take place effectively and efficiently.

Syllabus

SKI teachers MA Manba'ul Huda and MA Nurrohmah have developed the syllabus well. The syllabus consists of identification, competency standards, basic competencies and main material, teaching activities. This is according to the Ministry of Education and Culture's Education and Training Center (2016: 13). In preparing the syllabus, SKI teachers MA Manba'ul Huda and MA Nurrohmah took several steps, namely: reviewing Competency Standards and Basic Competencies. Competency Standards and Basic Competencies can be taken from content standards which are usually standard, except that those which do not yet exist can be prepared by the syllabus compiler/developer themselves. The next step is identifying the main/learning material, identifying the main/learning material that supports the achievement of basic competencies by considering: student potential, relevance to regional characteristics, level of physical, intellectual, emotional, social and spiritual development of students, usefulness for students, scientific structure, actuality, depth and breadth of teaching material, relevance to student needs and environmental demands.

Then the SKI teacher develops teaching activities. Teaching activities are designed to provide teaching experiences that involve mental and physical processes through interactions between students, students and educators, the environment and other teaching resources in order to achieve basic competencies. Things to pay attention to in developing teaching activities are that teaching activities are designed to provide assistance to educators, especially educators, so that they can carry out the teaching process professionally. Teaching activities contain a series of activities that must be carried out by students sequentially to achieve basic competencies.

SKI teachers formulate achievement indicators. Competency Indicators are markers of the achievement of basic competencies which are characterized by measurable changes in behavior which include attitudes, knowledge and skills. Indicators are developed according to the characteristics of students, subjects, educational units, regional potential and are formulated in operational verbs that are measurable and/or observable. Indicators are used as a basis for developing evaluation tools.

The SKI teacher determines the type of evaluation. Evaluation of students' achievement of basic competencies is carried out based on indicators. Evaluation is carried out using tests and non-tests in written and oral form, performance observations, attitude measurements, evaluation of work results in the form of assignments, projects and/or products, use of portfolios, and self-evaluation. The evaluation system must be adjusted to the teaching experiences undertaken in the teaching process.

The next step is for the SKI teacher to determine the allocation. Time for determining time allocation for each basic competency is based on the number of effective weeks and time allocation for subjects per week by considering the number of basic competencies, breadth,

depth, level of difficulty and level of importance of basic competencies. The time allocation listed in the syllabus is an estimate of the average time to master the basic competencies required by various students. SKI teachers determine teaching resources. The steps for developing the Syllabus are based on the Ministry of Education and Culture's Employee Education and Training Center Team (2016; 14-16). In this way, the SKI teachers MA Manba'ul Huda and MA Nurrohmah have prepared the syllabus well. The definition of syllabus is explained in Government Regulation (PP) no. 13 of 2015.

Teaching Implementation Plan

Based on Minister of Education and Culture Regulation Number 103 of 2014 concerning teaching in Basic Education and Secondary Education, the components and systematics of the teaching Implementation Plan (RPP) are determined. In preparing the RPP, SKI teachers Manba'ul Huda and MA Nurrohmah took several steps based on the Ministry of Education and Culture's Pusdiklat Team (2016: 22):

Review SKL, SK/KI-KD, indicators and syllabus to explore competency achievements and identify opportunities for customer activities

Determine identity, which includes: a) Study Group, namely the name needed to achieve KD and study load

Write down the Competency Standards/core competencies/stages for achieving development in the syllabus.

Rewrite the basic competencies in the syllabus.

Write down the indicators that have been formulated in the syllabus.

Formulate teaching objectives. Teaching objectives describe the teaching process and outcomes that students are expected to achieve in accordance with KD. The formulation of teaching objectives must refer to SK, KD and indicators using operational verbs that can be observed and measured. Teaching objectives can be organized to cover all KD or organized at each meeting.

Based on the steps above, teachers MA Manba'ul Huda and MA Nurrohmah have prepared the lesson plan well. The lesson plans that have been prepared by SKI teachers at MA Manba'ul Huda and MA Nurrohmah are in accordance with the 2013 curriculum. The format of the lesson plans prepared based on data obtained by researchers is in accordance with Minister of Education and Culture Regulation No. 81A of 2013 concerning the preparation of the 2013 curriculum RPP which states that: A teaching Implementation Plan is a teaching plan that is developed in detail from a particular main material or theme that refers to the syllabus. The RPP for the History of Islamic Culture is in accordance with Minister of National Education Regulation no. 65 of 2013 concerning Primary and Secondary Education Process Standards in the 2013 curriculum, states that teaching objectives are applied with competency standards, core competencies and indicators, which are described in detail about the competencies expected after the teaching process is completed.

Teaching Organizing of Islamic Cultural History (SKI) multimedia-based to Improve Students' Akhlakul Karimah

Teaching Organizing is a process of determining, grouping and arranging various activities needed to achieve goals, placing people in each activity, providing the necessary tools, determining authority that is relatively delegated to each individual who will carry out the activities. (Hasibuan, 2007: 19).

SKI teachers Manba'ul Huda and MA Nurrohmah have carried out the organization well because they have carried out the organizing steps according to T. Hani Handoko (1999). The organizing process is shown in the following three procedural steps:

Details of all activities that must be carried out to achieve organizational goals

Division of the total workload into activities that can logically be carried out by one person. This division of work should not be too heavy nor too light

Procurement and development of a mechanism to coordinate the work of organizational members into an integrated and harmonious unit.

Curriculum

Curriculum means a number of knowledge or subjects that students must take and complete in order to achieve a level or diploma. The curriculum used at MA Manba'ul Huda and MA Nurrohmah is the independent curriculum for class X and for class XI and class XII. 2013. The 2013 curriculum contains activities: observing, asking questions, gathering information, associating, communicating. This is in accordance with Minister of Education and Culture Regulation no. 103 of 2014. observing, asking, gathering information, associating, and communicating are the stages of teaching in the 2013 curriculum with a scientific approach which is student-centered learning.

The 2013 curriculum encourages and prioritizes student activity to develop understanding of knowledge, skills and spiritual and social attitudes in students. So students have to do a lot of activities, move a lot, interact a lot, discuss a lot, do a lot of group work, explore a lot of knowledge, observe a lot, ask a lot, gather information a lot, associate a lot, communicate a lot. All this will increase the dynamics in the class.

Teaching Materials

SKI teachers MA Manba'ul Huda and MA Nurrohmah prepare teaching materials in accordance with teaching materials based on the syllabus. Teaching material is the content of a curriculum, namely in the form of subjects or fields of study with topics, sub-topics and detailed explanations. The purpose of implementing teaching is visible in the teaching material delivered to students. Syaiful Bahri Djamarah explained that teaching material is the essence of what will be conveyed in the implementation of learning. Without teaching materials, the implementation of teaching will not run well (Djamarah in Umami: 2020, 9). Teachers pay attention to the criteria in selecting teaching materials, including that the material must match the teaching objectives, the teaching material must be explained, the material is in accordance with student needs, the

material is structured. SKI teachers in determining the teaching materials given to students need to be chosen appropriately, so that they can help students achieve competency standards and the teaching objectives they wish to achieve. Based on the research results, SKI teachers provide teaching materials such as books. The teacher refers to the teacher's book, student's book, and books that are relevant to the teaching material. According to the Directorate of Senior High School Development (2008:6), teaching materials are all forms of materials used to assist teachers in carrying out teaching and learning activities. The material in question can be written or unwritten material. Meanwhile, according to Koesnandar (2008:6), the types of teaching materials based on subject consist of two types, including: (a) teaching materials that are deliberately designed for learning, such as books, handouts, worksheets and modules; (b) teaching materials that are not designed but can be used for learning, for example clippings, newspapers, films, advertisements or news.

Teaching Media

Looking at the lesson plans prepared by SKI teachers at MA Manba'ul Huda and MA Nurrohmah regarding the use of teaching media, SKI teachers use teaching media such as picture media, power point media and textbooks, and use teaching Aids (ABP). Teaching Aids (ABP) include whiteboards, markers and LCDs when using power point media or watching videos. Based on the explanation above, there are various types of teaching media used by teachers, such as image media, power points, and print media (books). Meanwhile, the teaching aids used are whiteboards, markers and LCD/projectors.

SKI teachers have used teaching media in accordance with the teaching material presented. This is in accordance with Sadiman's opinion in Rani et al (2019: 9) who state that media is anything that can be used to channel messages from the sender to the recipient so that it can stimulate students' thoughts, feelings, attention and interests in such a way that the teaching process occurs.

SKI teachers use various teaching media. This aims to attract students' attention, to make it easier for students to absorb the knowledge provided by the teacher, so that students have cognitive, affectional and compensatory abilities. Levie & Lentz (1982) proposed four functions of teaching media in the Teaching and Learning process, especially visual media: (1) attention function, (2) affective function, (3) cognitive function, (4) compensatory function.

SKI teachers MA Manba'ul Huda and MA Nurrohmah use multimedia because of its many advantages, namely: students can learn according to their abilities and desires, students learn from teachers who are patient like computers and follow technological developments. This is in accordance with Fenrich in Munir (2013) concluding that the advantages of multimedia teaching include: a. Students can learn according to their abilities, readiness and desires; b. Students learn from 'patient' tutors (like computers) who adapt to the students' abilities; c. Students will be encouraged to pursue knowledge and receive instant feedback; d. Students are familiar with information and communication technology devices; e. Providing new experiences for students; f. Keep up with developments in science and technology. Apart from advantages, multimedia also has disadvantages.

Teaching Model

SKI teachers at Madrasah Aliyah Manba'ul Huda and Madrasah Aliyah Nurrohmah use Discoveryteaching and Problem Basedteaching learning models. This teaching model is often used because the Discoveryteaching learning model is one of the more activeteaching activities, because it contains a number of mental processes carried out by students (Rutonga, 2017). The Discoveryteaching model is one of the more activeteaching activities, because it includes There are a number of mental processes carried out by students (Rutonga, 2017) in Didik, 2022: 2) which can provide a stimulus for students to be more critical, active and communicative. Problem Basedteaching is ateaching model that uses problems as a focus to develop problem solving skills. This is in line with Hmelo-Silver in Nafiah (2014: 6).

Teaching Resources

Teaching sources are essentially anything, whether objects, data, facts, ideas, people, etc. that can lead to ateaching process. For example, package books, modules, LKS (student worksheets), realia, models, markets, banks, museums, zoos and markets (Prastowo in Samsinar, 2019: 2)

Sudjana in Samsinar (2019: 4) dividesteaching resources into several categories, namely:

Printedteaching sources: books, magazines, encyclopedias, brochures, newspapers, posters, floor plans, etc.

Non-printteaching sources: films, slides, videos, models, audio cassettes, etc.

teaching resources in the form of facilities: auditorium, library, study room, studio, sports field, etc.

teaching resources in the form of facilities: auditorium, library, study room, studio, sports field, etc.

teaching resources in the form of activities: interviews, group work, observation, simulations, games, etc.

teaching resources in the form of the environment: parks, museums, etc.

Because of the importance of material in learning, teachers must be clever in arranging material. To get a good composition of material, it is very necessary to take it from goodteaching sources. Thisteaching resource is very important. The choice ofteaching resources is not arbitrary. In selectingteaching resources teachers use certain criteria to selectteaching resources to be used. This is intended so that theteaching resources selected are appropriate and in accordance with theteaching objectives and are efficient when applied in learning. In the book Creative Guide to Making Innovative Teaching Materials (Prastowo, 2012: 61) explains that the criteria for selecting qualityteaching resources can be divided into 2, namely general criteria and specific criteria (ilmu-pendidikan.net, 2024, at 06:04).

General Criteria. General criteria for selecting quality teaching resources include:

- a) Economical, which means that teaching resources do not have to be expensive. Teaching resources need to be adjusted to the allocation of funds and the needs of the teaching resources to be used. As with economic principles, efforts need to be made to be able to obtain quality teaching resources that suit your needs with the minimum allocation of funds possible.
- b) Practical and simple, teaching resources must be easy to use and not confusing. No need for additional services or other tools that are difficult to provide.
- c) Easy to obtain, that teaching resources are easy to find and obtain. If necessary, you can take advantage of the available surrounding environment so that students can also easily take advantage of it
- d) Flexible or compatible, teaching resources do not have to be tied to a particular goal or teaching material. It would be better if it could be used for various teaching purposes and even other needs.

(2) Special Criteria

Specific criteria to consider when selecting quality teaching resources are as follows:

- a) teaching resources can motivate students to learn
- b) Learning resources for teaching purposes. This means that the teaching resources chosen should support the teaching and teaching activities carried out.
- c) teaching resources for research. This means that the teaching resources chosen should be able to be observed, analyzed, recorded carefully, and so on.
- d) teaching resources to solve problems. This means that the teaching resources chosen should be able to overcome student teaching problems faced in teaching and teaching activities.
- e) teaching resources for presentations. This means that the teaching resources chosen should be able to function as a tool, method or strategy for conveying messages.

SKI teachers MA Manba'ul Huda and MA Nurrohmah have used teaching resources appropriately. This is in accordance with the description of the criteria above.

Teaching Implementation of Islamic Cultural History (SKI) Multimedia-Based to Improve Students' Akhlakul Karimah

Teaching implementation is the application of the teaching plans that have been made. The implementation of SKI teaching has been carried out in accordance with the teaching Implementation Plan which has been prepared by SKI teachers MA Manba'ul Huda and MA Nurrohmah. According to Nana Sudjana in Jamil (2017: 119), the implementation of teaching is a process that is arranged in such a way according to certain steps so that the implementation achieves the expected results. According to Majid, the implementation of teaching is a teaching

and teaching process activity as a core element of teaching activities whose implementation is adjusted to the signs that have been prepared in previous planning. Implementation of teaching is a way of carrying out or presenting, explaining, giving examples, providing content exercises to students to achieve teaching objectives (Jamil, 2018: 119).

SKI teaching activities consist of pre-activities, core activities and closing activities. This is in line with Moh. Sopi'i et al (2019: 4) there are three stages of teaching implementation; 1) pre-learning activities are intended to prepare students to receive learning, 2) core teaching activities contain the application of teaching methods or media, 3) closing activities are stages used to reflect and carry out follow-up actions.

The implementation of SKI teaching about the Abbasid Daula uses multimedia. This is because:

- a) Multimedia is media that combines two or more elements consisting of text, graphics, images, audio, video and animation in an integrated manner. Multimedia is divided into two categories, namely: linear multimedia and interactive multimedia.
- b) Multimedia facilitates student-centered teaching because students are given the freedom to choose their own teaching materials and learn at a level that suits themselves.
- c) Multimedia can be used to help students form a "mental model" that will make it easier for them to understand a concept.
- d) The use of multimedia can raise students' teaching motivation, because multimedia makes teaching presentations more interesting.
- e) Multimedia has features that other media do not have, namely that multimedia provides an interactive process and provides reciprocal convenience, meaning that multimedia gives students freedom in determining the topic of the teaching process and multimedia provides ease of systematic control in the teaching process.

Apart from that, based on the cone of experience revealed by Edgar Dale (in Latuheru, 1988: 10) that the acquisition of teaching outcomes through the sense of sight and hearing is 75%, through the sense of hearing 13% and through other senses around 12%. Multimedia is a combination of various media (text, sound, images, animation and video) with tools and connections as a means of conveying messages. Multimedia is used to channel messages from the sender to the recipient so that it can stimulate students' thoughts, feelings, attention and interests which lead to the teaching process. This means that multimedia consists of various media which can be a means of interacting using the senses they have to carry out teaching activities so as to provide a lot of experiences that can educate people who learn quickly (Wuwuh Asrining, 2016: 13)

From the research above, it can be concluded how the teaching material can be achieved if in teaching and teaching activities teachers only rely on lectures, according to Edgar Dale, only 13%. Other research results show that teaching and teaching activities will be more effective and easier if assisted by visual means, where 11% of what is learned occurs through the sense of hearing, while 83% occurs through the sense of sight. Besides that, it is stated that we can only remember 20% of what we hear, but can remember 50% of what we see and hear. By

using multimedia, SKI teaching can improve students' akhlakul karimahs. By using multimedia, material that is abstract and outside students' daily experience can be understood, students do not feel bored and difficult material becomes easier.

With the existence of educational technology, it will be easier to produce educational media. From experience, teachers are starting to learn that students have different ways of learning, some learn faster through audio-visuals, some learn faster through audio, some prefer using print media, others through multimedia and so on (Sadiman, 2002: 9).

Teaching Evaluation of Islamic Cultural History (SKI) Multimedia-Based to Improve Students' Akhlakul Karimah

To determine the achievement of SKI learning, SKI teachers MA Manba'ul Huda and MA Nurrohmah have the task of carrying out an evaluation. This is in accordance with Rusman (2013: 11) that evaluation is part of the teacher's duties which is carried out after teaching activities take place with the aim of knowing the level of success of students in achieving teaching goals, so that teachers can make follow-up efforts to student teaching outcomes.

This is in accordance with the opinion of Elis (2014: 28) that evaluation of teaching outcomes is a process or activity to measure and assess several students' abilities in teaching such as knowledge, attitudes and skills in order to inform delegates about the status of the students' abilities.

Other evaluations include work evaluations in the form of assignments, portfolios and self-evaluations. The portfolio evaluation carried out by SKI MA teacher Manba'ul Huda was making canvases, posters, quotes. The average knowledge and skills score for XI MIA is above the KKM. Class XI IIS results for knowledge and skills scores above KKM. The spiritual attitude of MA Manba'ul Huda students, I am happy that Islam has an extraordinary history is good. The indicator that I believe in the truth of Islam is good. I pray that being able to pursue higher education will be very good, I pray that Islamic scientists will be reborn well, I pray that scientists will be rewarded with the best reply 3.15789. As for the social attitudes of students with the indicator that I am interested in studying the history of science in the Islamic world, I get good results, I kiss the teacher's hand when I meet them, I get a good average score, I kiss my parents when I leave school with a very good average, I look after the books and keep them. neatly is very good and I want to tell my friends about the history of science in the world it is good. SKI teacher MA Nurrohmah carries out formative evaluations, namely by observation. This observation is observing student discussions, the result of which is that most students actively participate in discussions. Thus the results are very good. The skills evaluation carried out by SKI teacher MA Nurrohmah included making concept maps or making schemes on cardboard.

Akhlakul karimah traits can be identified in two groups, namely: a) Commendable akhlakul karimahs (al-akhlak al-mahmudah): these are akhlakul karimahs that do not conflict with the Qur'an and al-Sunnah; b) Disgraceful akhlakul karimahs (al-akhlak al-madzumah). If the action is not in line with the teachings in the Islamic religion, it is called disgraceful akhlakul karimahs. A person with a feeling of fear of the Creator in his heart will not commit major sins,

while a person who has no fear in his chest means he does not believe in His punishment or punishment, he will even dare to change the order and turn away from it (Imam Al-Ghazali, in Surya Rizki RSP, 2021: 26).

CONCLUSION

Multimedia-based of Islamic Cultural History of teaching management to improve student's akhlakul karimah at MA Manba'ul Huda and MA Nurrohmah are in accordance with George R. Terry's principles so that students' akhlakul karimah improve.

Well-structured can improve students' akhlakul karimah at MA Manbaul Huda and MA Nurrohmah. Students always pray five times a day, are enthusiastic about imitating everything that the Messenger of Allah did, have a high enthusiasm for learning, are polite towards their parents, teachers and friends.

References

- 1) Al-Qur'an Karim.
- 2) Bakar, A.A. (1991). Pendidikan Karya Mendidik Akhlak Manusia Karya Filosof Islam Indonesia. Solo:CV Ramadhani
- 3) Adib, M. (2010). Filsafat Ilmu. Yogyakarta : Pustaka Pelajar
- 4) Ahmad sodiqiy dan Djunaidatul Munawwarah, 2011, Modul Pengembangan Perangkatpembelajaran PAI, Samarinda:T.tp,
- 5) Asiah, N. (2016). Pemikiran Al-Ghazali Progresif Dalam Pendidikan Inovatif. (Bandar Lampung: Fakta Press)
- 6) Darmawan, D. (2012). *Pendidikan Teknologi Informasi dan Komunikasi*. Bandung: PT Remaja Rosdakarya
- 7) Djamarah, S.B. & Aswan. (2010). *Strategi Belajar Mengajar*. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta
- 8) Fauzi, I.. (2012). *Manajemen Pendidikan ala Rasulullah*. Jogjakarta: Ar-Ruzz Media
- 9) Gafur, A.. (2012). *Desain Pembelajaran: Konsep, Model, dan Aplikasinya Dalam Perencanaan Pelaksanaan Pembelajaran*. Yogyakarta: Ombak
- 10) Hamalik, O. (2017). *Proses Belajar Mengajar* . Jakarta : Bumi Aksara
- 11) Handoko, T.H. (1999). *Manajemen*. Yogyakarta: BPFE
- 12) Hasibuan, M.SP. (2014). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Cetakan ke-14. (Jakarta Penerbit : Bumi Aksara)
- 13) Helmawati. (2014). *Pendidikan Keluarga*. Bandung: PT. Remaja Rosdakarya.
- 14) Husaini, U. (2008). *Metodologi Penelitian Sosial*. Jakarta: Bumi Aksara
- 15) Koesnandar. (2008). Pengembangan Bahan Belajar berbasis Web.
- 16) Komariah, A. & Satori, D. (2010). *Metodologi Penelitian Kualitatif*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- 17) Majid, A.(2014). *Strategi Pembelajaran*. (Bandung PT Remaja Rosdakarya)
- 18) Mansur.(2004). *Peradaban Islam dalam Lintasan Sejarah*. Yogyakarta: Global Pustaka Utama.
- 19) Nata, A. (1996). *Akhlak Tasawuf*. Jakarta: PT. Raja Grafindo Persada.

- 20) Prastowo, A. (2012). *Panduan Kreatif Membuat Bahan Ajar Inovatif*. Yogyakarta: Diva Press. Cetakan 5
- 21) Pusdiklat Kemendikbud
- 22) Rusman. (2012). *Model-Model Pembelajaran : Mengembangkan Profesionalisme Guru*, Bandung : CV. Alfabeta.
- 23) _____(2017), *PENGEMBANGAN INSTRUMEN DAN PENELITIAN*. SLEMAN : KALIMEDIA
- 24) Sagala, S. (2008). *Konsep dan Makna Pembelajaran*. Bandung: Alfabeta
- 25) Sanusi, A. (2014). *Sistem Nilai*. Bandung: Nuansa Cendikia.
- 26) Sa'ud, Udin S. (2011). *Inovasi Pendidikan*. Bandung : Alfabeta
- 27) Sudjana, N. (2010). *Dasar-dasar Proses Belajar*. (Bandung: Sinar Baru)
- 28) _____(2011). *Penilaian Hasil dan Proses Belajar Mengajar*. Bandung: Rosda Karya
- 29) Suryani, N. dkk., (2012). *Strategi Belajar Mengajar*. Yogyakarta : Ombak
- 30) Susanto, A. (2013). *Teori Belajar dan Pembelajaran di Sekolah Dasar*. Jakarta: Kencana Prenadamedia Group
- 31) Syah, M. (2003). *Psikologi Pendidikan*. Bandung: Remaja Rosdakarya.
- 32) Tulus, T. (2004). *Peran Disiplin pada Perilaku dan Prestasi Siswa*. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta.
- 33) Asrining, W. (2016). *Pemanfaatan Multimedia untuk Mendukung Kualitas Pembelajaran*. Prosiding Temu Ilmiah Nasional Guru (Ting) VIII. Universitas Terbuka Convention Center, Surabaya
- 34) Atika, Y., & Lestari, R. A. (2023). *Konstruktivistik Dalam Proses Pembelajaran Pendidikan Agama Islam (Studi Di SDUA Taman Harapan Curup) Institut Agama Islam Negeri Curup, Bengkulu Bengkulu Jurnal Bintang Pendidikan Indonesia (JUBPI) Vol.1, No.1*
- 35) Budyastuti, Y. & Fauziati, E. (2021). *Penerapan Teori Konstruktivisme pada Pembelajaran Daring*
- 36) *Interaktif*. Universitas Muhammadiyah Surakarta, Indonesia. *Jurnal Papeda*: Vol 3, No 2.
- 37) Didik Muhammad Fikri Sunarto.(2022). *Penggunaan Model Discoveryteaching Guna menciptakan kemandirian dan kreativitas Peserta*. *Pendidikan Bahasa dan Sastra*, Volume 21 Nomor 1 Januari 2022. Universitas Muhammadiyah.
- 38) <http://journal.unj.ac.id/unj/index.php/bahtera/> P-ISSN 0853-2710
- 39) Fajri, Z. (2019). *Model Pembelajaran Discoveryteaching Dalam Meningkatkan Prestasi Belajar Siswa SD*. *Jurnal IKA*. 7 (2)
- 40) Nur Amalia. (2022). *Universitas Muhammadiyah Prof. Dr.Hamka, Indonesia*. Published: 2022-01-30, halaman 2
- 41) Hendra, M. (2022). *Strategi guru dalam memilih berbagai metode pada pembelajaran*
- 42) Kamsinah. (2008). *Metode Dalam Proses Pembelajaran*. Studi tentang ragam dan Implementasinya.lentera pendidikan vol. 11 No. 1 Juni 2008
- 43) Karim, A. *Belajar Sejarah Kebudayaan Melalui Metode Pembelajaran Mind Mapping*. STAIN Kudus
- 44) Permata, L.D., Rahmawati, D., & Fitriana, L. (2018). *Pembelajaran Matematika SMP dalam Perspektif Landasan Filsafat Konstruktivisme*. *Jurnal Elektronik Pembelajaran Matematika*. Vol.5, No.1 .

- 45) Moh Sopi'i, Barowi, & Moh Nasuka. (2019). Manajemen Pembelajaran Mata Pelajaran Takhasus Pada MA Martabiyatul Banin Di Pekalongan Winong Pati. Pascasarjana UNISNU Jepara. Jurnal Intelegensia - Vol. 07 No. 2 Juli-Desember 2019 halaman 4
- 46) Muhlasin. (2019). Manajemen Pembelajaran dalam Rangka Meningkatkan Prestasi Belajar. Akademika: Vol 15. No. 1,
- 47) Nahidh, M. I., Aini, D. & Rosyida E.F. (2021). Manajemen Program Perencanaan, Pelaksanaan, dan Evaluasi Munadharah 'Ilmiah Pekan Arabi di Masa Pandemi, Vol. 7 No. 2
- 48) Nurhayati, (2014). Akhlak Dan Hubungannya Dengan Aqidah Dalam Islam. Jurnal Mudarrisuna 4 nomer 2
- 49) Nuraeni, C. (2020). Penerapan Model Pembelajaran Problem Basedteaching (PBL) untuk Meningkatkan Hasil Belajar IPS Siswa Kelas III SD Negeri Ciputih 01
- 50) Ramadhan, O. M. & Tarsono. (2020). Efektifitas pembelajaran sejarah kebudayaan Islam melalui google classroom ditinjau dari hasil belajar
- 51) Rianti, Ita, Saiful Bachri, dkk .(2016). Analisis Pembelajaran Sejarah Kebudayaan Islam Berbasis Kurikulum 2013 pada Materi Bani Abbasiyah Kelas XI IPS di MAN 1 Surakarta Tahun Ajaran 2015/2016. Volume 6, Nomor 2.
- 52) Rifaldi Dwi Syahputra. (2023). Manajemen Kreatif. Jurnal (MAKREJU) Vol.1 Nomer 3
- 53) Riffriyanti, E. (2019). Variasi Metode Pembelajaran Sejarah Kebudayaan Islam (SKI) di Mts Miftahul Ulum Weding Bonang Demak. Jurnal Studi dan Penelitian Pendidikan Islam Volume 2 Nomor 2
- 54) Samsinar, S. (2019). Urgensiteaching Resources (Sumber Belajar) Dalam Meningkatkan Kualitas Pembelajaran. Jurnal Kependidikan Vo. 13 Nomer 2.
- 55) Tishana, A. dkk. (2023). Filsafat Konstruktivisme dalam Mengembangkan Calon Pendidik pada Implementasi Merdeka Belajar di Sekolah Kejuruan Universitas Negeri Padang. Journal on Education Volume 05, No. 02, Website: <http://jonedu.org/index.php/joe>.
- 56) Umami Hanik Nashihah. (2020). Manajemen Pembelajaran Matematika Dalam Meningkatkan Minat Belajar Siswa SD Unggulan Muslimat NU Kabupaten Kudus. Volume 8, Nomor 1, 2020: 94-111. IAIN Kudus, Indonesia, halaman 9.
- 57) Peraturan Pemerintah (PP) No. 13 Tahun 2015
- 58) Undang-undang RI No. 20 Tahun 2003 tentang Sistem pendidikan
- 59) PMA Tahun 2008 Nomor 2 Tentang SKL Dan Standar Isi PAI dan Bahasa Arab di Madrasah
- 60) Pendidikan Nasional 2004
- 61) Permendikbud No. 81A Tahun 2013 tentang penyusunan RPP kurikulum 2013
- 62) Permendiknas Nomor 65 tahun 2013
- 63) Permendikbud No. 103 tahun 2014
- 64) Permendikbud RI Nomor 23 Tahun 2016 tentang Standar Evaluasi Pendidikan BAB II pasal 3
- 65) AL Hamdani. (2022). *Manajemen Pembelajaran SKI di MA Ibadurrahman Tibu Sisok Kecamatan Janapria*. Program Studi Pendidikan Agama Islam Fakultas Tarbiyah dan Keguruan Universitas Islam Negeri Mataram.
- 66) Desy Putri Angraeni. (2017). Penggunaan Media Pembelajaran Berbasis Multimedia Interaktif Visual untuk Meningkatkan Hasil Belajar Siswa pada Konsep Sistem Pernafasan. Skripsi. Program Studi Pendidikan Biologi FKIP Pasundan.

- 67) Husni I. (2008). *Pengembangan Multimedia Pembelajaran Berbantuan Komputer*, Karya Tulis Ilmiah, Fakultas Tarbiyah STAIN Manado
- 68) Iyang E.N. (2020). *Implementasi Teori Belajar Konstruktivisme pada Pembelajaran Pendidikan Agama Islam di SMA Negeri 22 Gowa*. TESIS Pascasarjana UIN Alauddin Makassar
- 69) Rizki S. (2021). *Akhlak menurut Al-ghazali (1059M – 1111 M) dan Ibnu Miskawai (932 M – 1030 M)*. Skripsi thesis UIN Sultan Syarif Kasim Riau.
- 70) <https://eprints.uny.ac.id/65664/3/BAB%20II.pdf>, diakses 11/10/2023, pukul 23: 15)
- 71) <https://serupa.id/model-pembelajaran-pengertian-ciri-jenis-macam-contoh/#> diakses 14/12/2023, pukul 11:38)
- 72) (<https://katulis.com/pengertian-multimedia-pembelajaran-menurut-para-ahli/>), diakses 20/01/2024.
- 73) https://www.google.co.id/search?sca_esv=600891144&q=gambar, diakses pada 24/01/2024, pukul 06:20)
- 74) <https://www.quipper.com/id/blog/info-guru>) diakses pada 24/01/2024, pukul 17.19
- 75) <http://zainal354.blogspot.com/2012/10/v-chaviorurldefaultvml.html>).
- 76) (<https://serupa.id/evaluasi-pembelajaran>, diakses 12/01/2024, pukul 21:40)
- 77) (<https://salamadian.com/pengertian-multimedia>) :
- 78) (<https://kumparan.com/berita-terkini/memahami-makna-akhlak-menurut-imam-al-ghazali-1zT8n6TYDGQ/3>).
- 79) <https://www.google.com/search?q=gambara+pendekatan>,
- 80) <https://katadata.co.id/safrezi/berita/61fca0b28c533/silabus-adalah-rencana-pembelajaran-berikut-panduannya>)
- 81) <https://ilmu-pendidikan.net/pembelajaran/sumber-belajar/kriteria-pemilihan-sumber-belajar-berkualitas>, diakses 28/03/2024, pukul 06: 04